

THE INFLUENCE OF ANTHROPOMORPHISM IN ENGLISH CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

Damekhan Ayimbetova,

Uzbek State World Languages University,
department of Linguistics and Literature,

E-mail: danyaimbetova@gmail.com

Abstract: The article is devoted to anthropomorphism in children's literature. Children's books and fairy tales help to learn the language and the benefits of picture books for children's language development. Picture books are a valuable source when it comes to children's learning of new concepts, language, and lessons have reviewed a body of findings on the impact of picture book features on children's learning and transfer of words and letters, science concepts, and problem solutions from picture books. The review focuses on how the three key developmental factors such as symbolic development, analogical reasoning, and reasoning about fantasy may have an impact on children's learning and transfer from books to the real world.

Keywords: children's literature, children's books, Burke, Copenhaver, Fabulous Histories by Sarah Trimmer, Anna Swell, The Black Beauty, Peter the Rabbit, Beatrix Potter.

Anthropomorphism is the name for the process of assigning human traits to non-human entities, and it has a long and lively presence in children's literature. From dancing dogs to wily wolves, cars to candelabras, popular texts for children rely heavily on non-human dialogue. The reasons for this are both historical and psychological. Many ancient cultures generated their creation stories using the flora and fauna of their surroundings as touchstones. These were stories for all members of a community, however, not necessarily for children. Printed books for children, in the British and European tradition, began to appear in the mid of 1600s. According to the British Library, the first picture book with animals as characters is the 1659 title *Orbis sensualism pictus*. This uses animal references to encourage children to mimic animal sounds as a means of learning the alphabet – and early phonics textbook.

Fictional children's stories intended for amusement as well as education did not appear on the literary horizon until well into the 18th century. This coincided with a general re-evaluation of what it meant to be a child, in line with the emergence of the first 'middle classes', compulsory primary education, and a desire for people across all levels of society to enjoy 'leisure time' These social developments opened the door for

all kinds of new moral stories for children – and picture books were teaching opportunities. The 18th and 19th centuries also saw a surge in naturalists avidly discovering and classifying new species of birds and animals from the colonial outposts. Children’s books of the time reflect this keen interest in the ‘personality’ of animals. So, while history delivered the perfect conditions for the inclusion of animals as lead characters in children’s books, it was educational psychology that kept them there.

Children’s books exist for several purposes: mainly literacy education, moral education, and pleasure. The most popular is a smart combination of all three – offering the pleasure of an engaging story, with an adult-pleasing lesson or two, and an underlying benefit of literacy enhancement. May Gibbs’ creative tales are a stellar example of this type of three-pronged impact. Animals as characters, therefore, can bring silliness and incongruity, making a story more enjoyable. But they also add a degree of emotional distance for the reader, which is important when the story message is personal, painful, or powerful.

“Having animals do the acting and mistake-making allows the face-saving emotional distance often needed to be able to join the conversation,” mentioned scholars Burke and Copenhaver³⁹. When the Three Little Pigs lose house after house, we roll along with the rhyme; the same situation involving homeless children is far less palatable. The Ugly Duckling draws gentle empathy, whilst ‘The Ugly Child’ would be frightening and confronting. Many children’s stories also use the trope of absent adults as a strategy. Disney tales include orphans a-plenty. Blyton sends The Famous Five off on camping adventures so they can learn from each other away from the gaze of memorializing adults. This story device is balanced, however, by watchful animals. Disney’s anthropomorphized woodland creatures follow their wards around, offering wisdom and comfort.

Some of the best children’s stories have animal main characters. Those anthropomorphic animals have human-like characteristics; they wear cloth, talk, go to work, have feelings, etc. Anthropomorphism enables young readers to understand more complex subjects or issues since topics are adapted to children’s worldviews.

Initially, anthropomorphic stories had a more significant purpose than entertaining children. They were rather used to teach children moral lessons humorously and creatively, appropriate manners and behaviors messages, and ideas are often conveyed by analogy. That is, animal characters are given similar traits and feelings as children so that the story becomes more accessible to the young audience. Children engage in these anthropomorphic stories from early childhood and pass those

³⁹Carolyn L. Burke, Joby G. Copenhaver *Animals as People in Children’s Literature*

stories on to their children so that anthropomorphism continues to evolve as a significant tool for engaging young readers.

The content of this chapter is concerned with anthropomorphic animal stories that are aimed at children. The main question of this paper is what effect anthropomorphic animal stories have on children's view of animals and how do children benefit from those stories in terms of their learning results. That is, does anthropomorphism enable children to learn about the real animal and its biology? How do animal representation and the language of the story influence children's learning? Moreover, this paper gives an insight into how these stories shape children's views on specific species. Concerning the means of analysis, this paper suggests that anthro-pomorphic stories do not increase children's knowledge about real animals, but rather illustrate an unrealistic image of animals and their biology. This paper does not analyze a specific story but gives an insight into a few studies that had been conducted concerning the impact anthro-pomorphic studies have on children.

Children's literature has many functions when it comes to learning; it does not only provide children with many opportunities to respond to literature, but it also gives allows them empathy, morality, creativity, and also an understanding of their own cultural her-itage and the culture of others. Moreover, children's literature can be used to foster children's growth of personality and social skills.

One valuable part of children's literature is the aspect of personality and social development. That is, children's literature can help to develop empathy towards people and to become less egocentric. Moreover, it can encourage children to build acceptance towards people that are different from the majority of people. Children's stories also have the strength to encourage their emotional intelligence and moral development. This is achieved through stories that ad-dress issues that are controversial or of philosophical concern. Furthermore, stories aimed at children provide the opportunity to learn about cultural heritage and the cultures of other people. This aspect is of relevance since it is crucial for children to develop a positive attitude towards different cultures. Therefore, it is important that stories are chosen which do not contain a ste-reotypical depiction of people from specific cultures. Another value of children's books is the aspect of creativity. Children's stories encourage the development of imagination and allow children to experience new situations from a safe distance. That is, they enable children access to the thoughts of a character and allow children to experience a situation from the eyes of a fictional character⁴⁰. There are many different types of children's stories, which serve different purposes. One of those genres

⁴⁰ Martha Crippen "The Value of Children's Literature" 2012

incorporates humanized as their main character. Children's tales about animals have a history that dates from the seventeenth century. Animal stories served educational purposes such as teaching the alphabet and learning to read, count, and helping children to understand the world. Examples like the 'Fabulous Histories' by Sarah Trimmer combine the story of a family of robins with a human family and aims to teach children about kindness and social duty. Trimmer created the robin family as a model for children from which they can learn behavior and sympathy towards one another. Moreover, robins represent the epitome of family life and have, therefore, also a symbolic meaning. Anna Swell's popular story 'The Black Beauty' (1877)⁴¹ was initially aimed at adult readers, but also became a children's story. Anna Swell's story tries to encourage readers to sympathize with horses and seeks to give a lesson about the proper treatment of horses. That is Swell sought to induce kindness, sympathy, and an understanding treatment of horses and an end to the cruel use of certain reins and blinkers⁴². Stories like 'Peter the Rabbit' (1902) by Beatrix Potter are also induced to teach children about proper behavior and the dangers that can be caused by disobedience. The humorous and adventurous story is characterized by Peter the Rabbit's disobedience which causes him trouble. The tale is about Peter the rabbit, who disobeys his mother and enters Mr. McGregor's garden, which is full of vegetables. He soon, is spotted by Mr. McGregor near the cucumber frame and is chased all over the garden and loses his jacket and his shoes. Peter the rabbit finally finds the gate and returns home frightened but wiser⁴³. Those stories convey a moral message that children could potentially transfer to their own behaviour and learn from them.

Picture books are a valuable source when it comes to children's learning of new concepts, language, and lessons have reviewed a body of findings on the impact of picture book features on children's learning and transfer of words and letters, science concepts, and problem solutions from picture books. The review focuses on how the three key developmental factors such as symbolic development, analogical reasoning, and reasoning about fantasy may have an impact on children's learning and transfer from books to the real world. Here, learning refers to the child's ability to recognize information that is presented in the book; transfer refers to their ability to apply new information to new contexts. However, it should be considered that the ability to transfer newly-acquired information to a new unknown context might be limited by "developments of their symbolic understanding, of fantasy and reality"⁴⁴.

⁴¹ Black Beauty: The Autobiography of a Horse was published in 1877

⁴² <https://www.bl.uk/press-releases/2014/november/2015-cultural-preview>

⁴³ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/The-Tale-of-Peter-Rabbit>

⁴⁴ Yeganeh Khodaparast The Impact of Anthropomorphic Animal Stories on Children's Learning

Strouse et al. claim that the difficult part of transferring new information to real-world settings is that of symbolic insight. Accordingly, children first need to recognize the book as an entity in itself as well as a symbolic source of information about the world. That is, when reading a book about a specific animal, children need to notice that depicted animal in the picture book as a representative of the same animal in the real world. The ability to recognize a picture in a book as an object that represents another entity is a symbolic task that children have to accomplish. In order to transfer complex information and concepts from picture books to the real world, children need more than only a symbolic insight. Thus, children have to activate a representation of that depicted animal in the book and remember all details about its appearance in order to correctly transfer the information to the real animal. More complex concepts, such as the ability of animals to use camouflage to hide from predators, requires children to recognise the abstract feature and apply those features to novel species⁴⁵.

In terms of children's analogical reasoning it seems that young children between the age of one and two, who are already experienced in one domain, are able to use deep features in order to solve analogical issues. But children who have a limited domain and conceptual knowledge are depended on the surface-level features when it comes to making an analogy and looking for commonalities among the species. More precisely, "if children's understanding of colour camouflage is tied to specific picture book illustrations (e.g., a frog) and surface features of that example (e.g., greenishness), they will likely fail to transfer the concept to other animals or contexts"⁴⁶. This aspect might be an issue when in terms of transferring information from picture books to the real-world, since picture books often enable access to content that children would not experience in their daily life. Young children, therefore, might face difficulties in terms of their analogical reasoning, since their understanding of a concept is tied to an illustration in a picture book, which is not representative of the real animals.

When it comes to learning from picture books it seems that children's capability to distinguish between reality and fiction, is an essential prerequisite. That is, children have to have developed the capacity to differentiate between fictional and realistic aspects in the story. This ability is particularly important when children have to extract unrealistic attributes of anthropomorphized animals and only transfer the factual information presented in the story. Strouse et al. note "children's learning from picture

⁴⁵ Gabrielle A. Strouse, Angela Nyhout, and Patricia A. Ganea "The Role of Book Features in Young Children's Transfer of Information from Picture Books to Real-World Contexts" <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00050>

⁴⁶ Gabrielle A. Strouse, Angela Nyhout, and Patricia A. Ganea "The Role of Book Features in Young Children's Transfer of Information from Picture Books to Real-World Contexts" <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00050>

books must be selective in that they have to separate what information is fictional versus what could be true in reality”⁴⁷.

This ability might depend on children’s capacity to recognize the story as something and to classify what the something represents. Anthropomorphic stories and illustrations of animals, therefore, might challenge children’s ability to distinguish between fact and fiction and their reasoning about real-life animals. Strouse et al. argue that storybooks with realistic content might be more supportive when learning about the biology of animals or scientific concepts. Storybooks also seem like a great source in terms of children’s language development. Strouse et al. looked at studies that focused on word learning from picture books with manipulative features, such as scratch and sniff or lift-or-flap books. The studies revealed that if learning new words, such as the name of an animal, is the focus manipulative features in books tend to be more distracting than supportive. Hence, manipulative features seem to be more distracting from the learning issue, rather than helping them to learn new vocabulary. The researcher concludes that “if the goal is to teach children new words or letters, it appears that books with realistic images are best, especially with the youngest children. If books with manipulative features are selected, they should draw attention to the educational content rather than distract from it”⁴⁸. Conclusively, not all kinds of picture books are beneficial for children’s language development. It should be paid attention to the sort of manipulative features and whether they might distract children from the learning content.

The children’s developmental stage has a major impact on their learning. Some developmental aspects such as the ability to differentiate between reality and fantasy might be crucial when it comes to selecting transferable information from picture books to a real-life situation or an animal. Therefore, children’s age and goal of learning should be taken into account when choosing a picture book.

⁴⁷ Gabrielle A. Strouse, Angela Nyhout, and Patricia A. Ganea “The Role of Book Features in Young Children's Transfer of Information from Picture Books to Real-World Contexts” <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00050>

⁴⁸ Gabrielle A. Strouse, Angela Nyhout, and Patricia A. Ganea “The Role of Book Features in Young Children's Transfer of Information from Picture Books to Real-World Contexts” <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00050>

REFERENCES:

1. Black Beauty: The Autobiography of a Horse was published in 1877
2. Carolyn L. Burke, Joby G. Copenhaver Animals as People in Children's Literature
3. Martha Crippen "The Value of Children's Literature" 2012
4. Yeganeh Khodaparast The Impact of Anthropomorphic Animal Stories on Children's Learning
5. Gabrielle A. Strouse, Angela Nyhout, and Patricia A. Ganea "The Role of Book Features in Young Children's Transfer of Information from Picture Books to Real-World Contexts"
6. <https://www.bl.uk/press-releases/2014/november/2015-cultural-preview>
7. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/The-Tale-of-Peter-Rabbit>
8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00050>